

3. Inhibition of the reaction by increase in concentration of I' is explained by shift of equilibrium in (ii) to the right, also by withdrawal of free I_2 in the equilibrium $I_2 + I' \rightleftharpoons I_3'$; inhibition through increase of $[H^+]$ by shift of equilibrium in eqn. (a) (p. 266) to the left.

4. The kinetics of the apparent catalytic reaction and the order of comparative efficiency of the various metals employed, as measured by the rate of disappearance of I_2 , is thus the net result of a number of simultaneous reactions of variable rates in (a, b, c, p. 268) and (ii). It has not been found possible so far to give quantitative expression to the latter, so as to be able to predict the comparative catalytic efficiency of the metal ions with the light intensity applied.

5. The general similarity in the experimental course of the reaction with all the metals employed indicates the existence of a number of co-ordination complex salts of hydroxy-carboxylic acids and manganese, chromium, cerium, cobalt and uranium, raised to at least a tervalent state, which have not yet been described.

It may be noted in conclusion that attempts which have appeared in the literature to study these reactions in the absence of KI *i.e.*, using I_2 in aqueous solution to commence with, apart from difficulties of measurement, do not appear to simplify the kinetics, since reaction, if it happens at all, is accompanied by the simultaneous production of I' .

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VELOCITY OF TRANSFORMATION OF 1 : 3 : 5 TRIKETONES INTO 2 : 6-DISUBSTITUTED γ -PYRONES. PART II

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Velocity of transformation of 1 : 3 : 5-triketones into γ -pyrones has been investigated and is found to be unimolecular like the standard substance, acetone dioxalic ester. It is therefore concluded that diacetylacetone and its homologues have open chain structure. The values of velocity constants depend on R-groups and is in the order: COOEt > CH_3 > C_2H_5 > C_3H_7 . The high value due to COOEt is due to its negativity. The velocity constant for acetylbenzoylacetone, which contains one positive and one negative group, is intermediate between the negative COOEt group and the positive groups, CH_3 , C_2H_5 and C_3H_7 .

In Part I of this paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 60) the authors have studied the velocity of transformation of acetonedioxalic ester into chelidonic ester with a view to investigating the structure of 1 : 3 : 5-triketones and obtained an unimolecular constant. The change is

Diacetylacetone ($\text{R-R}' = \text{CH}_3$) and its homologues ($\text{R-R}' = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or C_3H_7) under exactly identical conditions were found to behave exactly like the standard substance, giving 2:6-substituted dimethyl-, diethyl- and dipropyl- γ -pyrones. This supports independently the open chain structures of these compounds, verified chemically by Deshpande, Bedekar and Kaushal (*ibid.*, 1935, 12 465). In each case the reaction was found to be strictly unimolecular.

In case of acetone dioxalic ester, both physical and chemical methods were used for studying the rate of the reaction. However, with diacetylacetone and its homologues the physical method was found to be unsuitable because diacetylacetone is a low melting solid and its homologues are liquids, which are inconvenient for separation from medium and for weighing. The chemical method on the other hand was found to be satisfactory. These substances readily dissolve in 50% alcohol and copper salts are immediately precipitated by means of aqueous copper acetate solution. The pyrones formed are soluble in aqueous alcohol and hence are not precipitated. The copper salts were filtered at the pump, freed from the copper acetate by washing with water in which they are insoluble. It is observed that in all cases unimolecular constants are obtained, the reaction being as in the case of the standard substance, acetone dioxalic ester.

TABLE I

Velocity of transformation of diacetylacetone into dimethylpyrone.

Solvent = 50% aqueous methyl alcohol. Catalyst = 0.0402 *N*-HCl.

Temp. = 52°. Wt. of diacetylacetone = 1.7386 g. Vol. of the soln. = 50 c.c.

Time (t)	Wt. of Cu-salt proportional to unchanged triketone ($a-x$)	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$	Time (t)	Wt. of Cu-salt proportional to unchanged triketone ($a-x$)	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0 min.	0.1898 g.	—			
35	0.1726	0.00118	304 min.	0.0966 g.	0.00097
98	0.1567	0.00082	378	0.0820	0.00099
163	0.1310	0.00099	437	0.0748	0.00093
238	0.1104	0.00099	484	0.0652	0.00096

TABLE II

Velocity of transformation of dipropionylacetone into diethylpyrone.

Wt. of dipropionylacetone = 0.4874 g. Vol. = 50 c.c. Vol. of soln. precipitated as Cu salt each time = 4 c.c. Other conditions same as in Table I.

<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .	<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁
0 min.	0.0454 g.	—	321 min.	0.0320 g.	0.00048
60	0.0424	0.00049	376	0.0304	0.00047
178	0.0372	0.00048	471	0.0288	0.00048

TABLE III

Solvent = 80% aqueous methyl alcohol. Catalyst = 0.1036 *N*-HCl. Temp. = 62°. Wt. of dipropionyl acetone = 0.8782 g. Vol. = 25 c.c. Vol. ppted each time = 2 c.c.

<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .	<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .
0 min.	0.09397 g.	—	195 min.	0.0288 g.	0.0027
48	0.0698	0.0027	253	0.0178	0.0028
87	0.0548	0.0027	313	0.0114	0.0029
133	0.390	0.0028	355	0.0082	0.0029

TABLE IV

*Velocity of transformation of di-n-butyrylacetone into di-n-propylpyrone.*Solvent = 50% aqueous methyl alcohol. Catalyst = 0.402 *N*-HCl. Temp. = 52°. Wt. of di-*n*-butyrylacetone = 0.3628 g. Vol. of the solution = 50 c.c. Vol. of the soln. ppted each time = 4 c.c.

<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .	<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .
0 min.	0.0314 g.	—	326 min.	0.0206 g.	0.00056
70	0.0282	0.00059	471	0.0168	0.00057
215	0.0238	0.00056	565	0.0148	0.00057

TABLE V

*Velocity of transformation of acetylbenzoylacetone into 2-methyl-6-phenylpyrone.*Solvent = 80% aqueous methyl alcohol. Catalyst = 0.040-*N*-HCl. Temp. = 60°. Wt. of acetylbenzoylacetone = 0.6068 g. Vol. of the soln. = 100 c.c. Vol. of soln. ppted each time = 10 c.c.

<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .	<i>t.</i>	<i>a - x.</i>	<i>k</i> ₁ .
0 min.	0.0746 g.	—	240 min.	0.0194 g.	0.00243
60	0.0498	0.00291	300	0.0150	0.00242
120	0.0380	0.00244	360	0.0064	0.00280
180	0.0276	0.00240			

Comparison of the values of k_1 determined with the groups in the above reactions is given below :

TABLE VI

Groups	CO ₂ Et.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇	C ₆ H ₅
	and CO ₂ Et	and C ₆ H ₅	and CH ₃	and C ₃ H ₇	and C ₂ H ₅
k_1	0.0325	0.0024	0.00096	0.00058	0.00048
		(60° solvent 80% MeOH)			

The above table shows that the velocity constant as dependent on groups R are in the following order :—COOEt > CH₃ > C₃H₇ > C₂H₅, the very high value of the velocity constant due to the group COOEt is doubtless due to its acidic character. The velocity constant does not seem to depend on the weight of the group only, for the effect of C₃H₇ group is greater than that of C₂H₅. It appears that COOEt group, which is a negative group, confers maximum velocity to the reaction. All other remaining groups are positive. An interesting case arises when a triketone contains one positive and one negative group. This was realised in the case of acetylbenzoylacetone (R=CH₃, R'=C₆H₅) which changes into 2-methyl-6-phenylpyrone.

Here the velocity constant of the reaction, which was carried out under the same conditions as the other reactions as far as possible, was found to be less than for acetone dioxalic ester but greater than that for diacetylacetone.

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